

Flint artifacts from Gaasterland, Fryslân

Results of one year surface prospecting

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Samenvatting

In 2013 zijn bij archeologische veldprospecties rond Oudemirdum in het Gaasterland (provincie Fryslân) 128 prehistorische vuursteen artefacten gevonden. Deze blijken voor het merendeel te bestaan uit afslagen en kernen. Omdat ook geretoucheerde werktuigen voorkomen, lijken de prehistorische activiteiten zich niet te hebben beperkt tot de productie van vuursteen werktuigen, maar is een combinatie met de jacht heel goed mogelijk. Hoewel vanuit oppervlakte vondsten weinig harde conclusies mogelijk zijn, is in elk geval te stellen, dat het gebied rond Oudemirdum op vele plaatsen prehistorische activiteit laat zien, waarbij gids- artefacten wijzen op een periode in het Laat-Neolithicum/ Vroege Bronstijd. Een relatie met de Trechterbeker Cultuur, die in het Rijsterbosch een steenkist achterliet, is goed mogelijk, wanneer gekeken wordt naar technologische aspecten van het aangetroffen materiaal (artefacten op afslagen) en naar de locaties op droge zandgronden. Zolang geen opgravingen in Gaasterland zijn uitgevoerd, waarbij een duidelijk dateerbare context informatie kan geven over de chronologie van aangetroffen artefacten, is echter niets zeker en zullen we moeten volstaan met type- chronologiën of andere indirecte informatie zoals gids- artefacten. Dit artikel is vooral bedoeld als documentatie van de verzamelde artefacten en de conclusies

verbonden aan het aan het oppervlak verzamelde materiaal moeten dan ook met voorbehoud worden geïnterpreteerd. Met dank aan de diverse eigenaren/ pachters van de percelen voor het mogen betreden van de akkers.

Résumé

En 2013, pendant des prospections archéologiques, 128 artefacts ont été découverts autour d'Oudemirdum, dans la région sablonneuse de Gaasterland, province de Frise, Pays-Bas. La plupart des artefacts sont des éclats réguliers et des nucléus. Parce qu'il y a beaucoup d'outils (sur éclat et nucléus; outils comme des grattoirs, perçoirs) dans le total d'artefacts, les activités préhistoriques n'étaient pas seulement limitées à la production d'outils, mais une combinaison avec la chasse est bien possible. Malgré le fait que conclusions, basées sur des trouvailles de surface ne sont pas très fort, on peut dire que les environnements d'Oudemirdum montre une grande activité préhistorique, aussi visible par des artefacts de guide, attribuées au Néolithique final- Age de Bronze ancien. Une relation avec la Culture "Trechterbeker" (Culture Néolithique moyen- Néolithique final/ tardif) n'est pas totalement exclues, regardant l'aspect technologique (surtout d'artefacts sur éclats) et l'aspect de localisation des trouvailles, dans les zones les plus hautes et sablonneuses. Ainsi que le Gaasterland ne connaît pas des fouilles avec des artefacts provenant d'une stratigraphie datable, rien est sûr; il ne reste que des chronologies de type ou d'information indirecte des artefacts de guide.

Cet article n'est que seulement comme documentation des artefacts collectionnées en surface, avec des interprétations limitées. Remerciements aux propriétaires des terrains, pour l'accès aux terrains.

Summary

This article is written as a conclusive report after one year of field prospections in Gaasterland in the province of Fryslân in The Netherlands. In 2013, a total of 128 artifacts were discovered at ten different locations around the village of Oudemirdum. From these locations, two findspots were responsible for the majority of the finds, at the other findspots only few artifacts were discovered. In an analysis, it seemed that the artifacts were mainly consisting of flakes and cores while blade technology is rare. The artifacts are mainly consisting of flakes; so most likely these are originating from the broad Early- Neolithic to Early Bronze Age period. Most artifacts were found at two major findspots near Oudemirdum and indicating a local tool production, but meanwhile, as fifty percent of the artifacts fits in a 'tool – category', it seems that daily tasks were carried out as well, so it is quite possible we deal with (small?) seasonal camps with dual function: hunting, fishing and collecting on the one hand and tool production on the other. However, as the artifacts were surface- collected, no big conclusions can be hung on the artifacts and their relations, but it is clear prehistoric activity in this part of Gaasterland is not difficult to establish. As the majority of the finds will be of a later Neolithic date, so a possible relation with the *Trechterbeker Culture* (TRB) is not excluded, as this culture had flake -based tool manufacture and used cores as tools; but as no typical guide-artifacts from the TRB, like axe fragments or shards were found, this remains uncertain, till new finds bring more light on the subject.

The location of Gaasterland in the Benelux (red dot)

1. Introduction

During 2013, in the region of Gaasterland (province of Fryslân, the Netherlands), several locations have been prospected with the objective to search for any traces of prehistoric activity, in practice: flint artifacts. No further research questions were made.

As a result, a total of 128 flint artifacts have been surface collected in the period April - October 2013, thus reflecting prehistoric activity from different archaeological periods at ten different locations, which all are centered around the village of Oudemirdum, as these locations were most easily and quickly accessible; further examinations only were made in the woodland of the Rijsterbosch near Mirns and outside the region, in Workum, where some artifacts have been found, but this is not included in this article.

The preliminary results of a short analysis of flint tools from a specific location, OLW1 with fieldname “Hege Gerzen”, published in December 2013(1), are integrated in this article. This article presents an overview of surface collected flint artifacts, which can be useful with a view to recording documented material and moreover, for sharing information about finds for those who are interested in archaeological finds from a small region. So this article has been written for the sake of completeness and to round off one year of field prospecting. This is also the reason why, as an example a number of images of found artifacts are added to this article.

As the author is unknown with previous (surface) collected flint artifacts from Gaasterland, (except for some exceptional artifacts described in literature) this article must be regarded as a standalone article, so without references to other, similar finds from the same region (2). Though this causes some uncertainty about the position and validation of the collected material, the artifacts from itself are interesting enough to be presented and discussed. An analysis of the collected material has been made, to obtain information about average dimensions, flint type and tool types, with regard to possible tool production and prehistoric activities. As we deal with surface collected material, only some general information can be distilled from such analysis.

2. The region and its archaeology very briefly

Gaasterland is an elongated region, roughly located between the villages Warns/Hemelum in the west and the villages Sondel/ Wyckel in the east, forming a different landscape compared to the rest of the province Fryslân, as the landscape has been modeled by a Saalian end – moraine, some 140.000 years ago. This end- moraine formed the basic shape of a gently sloping region we consider today. During extreme glacial conditions of the Weichselian, in the complete absence of vegetation, this end- moraine has been covered by eolian sand-covers, mainly blown from the dry North- sea basin. Afterwards, the landscape has been modeled and leveled by erosion partially by human influence (e.g. after deforesting) causing sand displacement by strong winds; thus leveling the former elevations and filling up several former glacial depressions and brook valleys, a prolonged processes which have exerted a great influence on the landscape, that must be taken into consideration in today's field- prospection strategies.

The Saalian ice -cover transported exotic stones, including flint into this region, from South Sweden and Denmark, forming a raw material source for tool production since the Middle Paleolithic.

Evidence for such Middle Paleolithic presence is given by finds of some (parts of) bifaces found at Elahuizen and Hemelum and from the Upper Paleolithic evidence is given by tools of the Hamburg Culture, found near the hamlet of Kolderwolde (see e.g. a short overview in the book "Diggelgoud" (chapter by: Stapert & Johansen, 2008). Mesolithic evidence is given by finds from Warns, while the most popular, best known prehistoric remains are from the Rijsterbosch, where a stone coffin (megalithic structure) has been discovered in the 19th century, which has been excavated and is restored as an official monument today. This stone coffin was left by members of the *Trechterbeker Culture*, forming their memorial, but other evidence of occupancy by this culture in the region is absent, till today.

Gaasterland must have been more frequently visited during the transitional late Neolithic – Early Bronze Age period, mainly for hunting purposes, regarding the finds of four guide type artifacts (see also article at weblog Yn Gaasterlân on the internet).

During the Neolithic, the adjacent southern area of Gaasterland was large moorland with open waters and slowly flowing brooks (including the *Vecht* brook); it is only with the sea-level rise during and especially *after* the Roman Period the lake *Flevo* increasingly expanded, so the lake IJsselmeer was created, forming the southern boundary of the Gaasterland region since ca 600 AD; thus influencing a possible development of the region (especially Stavoren by the Hanze union). This expanding IJsselmeer also swallowed possible archaeological traces, as parts of the end- moraine disappeared, forming some steep cliffs (e.g. Oudemirdummer Klif, Rode Klif).

During the Late Early and High Middle Ages (800- 1000 AD) a part of the landscape seemed to have been deforested for human activities, mainly for agriculture; in this period the first small villages developed from possible scattered Late Iron Age 'settlements'.

Local economies were mainly based on agriculture, pottery production (e.g. at Oudemirdum) and fishery at the predecessor of the IJsselmeer, the *Zuiderzee*. In the Late Middle Ages and sub- recent period the holding of sheep became important, again causing more erosion in the landscape. The poor soil conditions in the biggest part of the sandy region of Gaasterland did not allow a big surplus for a rapidly increasing population, so the region had low numbers of inhabitants, compared to other regions. Still

Gaasterland is a low dense populated region in The Netherlands.

3. Field prospections and analysis: explaining some methods

Prospected fields were pre-selected by altitude (especially the relation between and curving of elevation intervals) in relation with geological conditions. Especially locations which were located in high, sandy areas near depressions (former open water) and south and south west oriented locations in former brook valleys were pre- selected. In this selection, the soil condition was the dominant factor to search for possible archaeological correlate.

The selected fields were at least three times systematic field walked(see survey months in the table below), depending on the prevailing weather conditions, the accessibility of the site, the period of permission to access the terrains, and potential visibility of artifacts in the field, e.g. in case artifacts are buried too deep in sand layers. In practice, presence of colluvial erosion at fields served as a predicting parameter for the find of possible artifacts at suitable locations.

2013

April	Mai	June	July	August	September	October
ORS1/2	ORS 1/2		OJB			ORS2
OHB			OFW			OLW1/2
	OBL					
	OBL2					
	OHB2					
	OBW					

Table 1, showing the periods terrains were visited.

Searching for stone artifacts in a sandy region like Gaasterland is not impossible, but quite complicated and demanding a certain effort, especially as possible Stone Age artifacts must be distinguished from natural flint at those locations where such flint is exposed. So a quantitative sampling method, limited to flint sometime was inevitable, to make the distinction between artifact (man-made flint object) and geofact (natural flint objects which look man-made) *after* the prospection.

The prospected terrains were divided into sub- sections, labeled 1/2 (main divisions in case of disturbed boundary) or depending on its dimensions and possible interesting findspots, into A-D or A-F as sub-divisions. Concentrations or surface scatters were listed separately. In other prospections, with the aim to find shards from the surface, this sub-division of fields seemed to be necessary, but for the terrains where flint artifacts were found, sub- divisions were not made.

The flint of the boulder clay region very often mimics man-made artifacts but is not (see e.g. edge damaging, Tringham et al. 1974). Many natural geofact appear as flakes, cores or blades, but even as produced tools like points, drills or knives.

This is also the reason, why so many collected objects – primary assumed artifacts - are finally categorized “Cf.” (confer) or even are rejected because of the lack of clear determination characteristics.

For this reason, all characteristics for artifacts were placed in a preconceived method, to avoid the collection of geofacts. This method includes the demands for accepted artifacts, with characteristics of man-made artifacts e.g. the presence of bulbs, ventral scars on bulbs, intentional secondary retouch, an overall commensurate weathering pattern, flaking patterns on cores (negatives) and combinations of these characteristics. The bulb- scar complex determination factor for artifacts is very important, but does not always give a reliable outcome, e.g. semi- finished points and used flint cores do not possess such features (see discussion below). So a part of the collected artifacts were afterwards classified Cf. (confer) instead of being rejected, but they are not taken into account; so the real numbers of artifacts, collected in the fields could be much higher. In the lithic analysis, possible plow damage or cryoturbation damage (causing natural edge retouch) and the collecting of parts of artifacts have been especially taken into account (see e.g. Malouf, 1982), again resulting in the rejection of small a part of the collected material.

Artifacts have been technological and typological analyzed for a focused objective to establish local tool production (technological) and possible prehistoric activity (typological) (3). Dimensions of the artifacts are measured, where always the maximum size has been taken, because of the big variability in length, width and thickness of the artifacts. E.g. the length of an artifact could be quite clear, but its width and thickness at the same time could vary up to 5 mm or more, depending on proximal or distal side, where proximal bulbs differ tremendous in dimensions from distal points at the same artifact. The analysis has been used for a comparison between the technological features of produced/used artifacts at the different sites. In such manner slight variations in production might distinguish the artifacts in different periods or cultural stages as some characteristics imply a certain period (like trapezes on *flakes* in the late TRB phase). As palimpsest building at favorite locations is expected, special attention has been given in variety of patinas, dimensions and tool production at a single site. The low numbers of flint artifacts, found at the majority of the visited locations (outside OLW and ORS) do not hamper the possible information derived from analysis of such small numbers and are therefore involved in the general conclusions.

Where flakes are mentioned, regular flakes are intended; for other flakes must be qualified as debitage flakes and this is mentioned in the text (e.g. decortication flake). In this report, the color of flint has been taken in analysis. Though many variations in colors are possible in local flint, ranging from white till black, from red to yellow, two major color types have been used for production of tools. These types are the grey color type, with many variations (e.g. grey- brownish, grey- black, grey and white) and the honey color type, also with many variations (e.g. more yellow or brownish or more orange colored).

ORS 1-004, an example of a honey colored flint type

ORS 1-024, an example of a grey colored flint type

Listed tool types in tables in the next paragraph are largely descriptive and not types in the formal sense, no sub-categories are used. In the total numbers of artifacts broken parts of blades/ flakes are counted, treated as equal units, so total numbers could be misconceived reading the tables (see Hiscock, 2002). For this article, while the position and possible relations of each artifact is unclear, this is of no real importance.

4. The artifacts by location; comparison between the locations; brief description of the locations and the found artifacts

Stone Age flint artifacts were noticed at following locations, named 'findspots' to distinguish them from 'sites', which latter are settlements. Only two locations might be regarded as possible sites, i.c. possible seasonal settlements or seasonal 'stops' (Oudemirdum *Rinia State* and Oudemirdum *Liemerige Wei*).

See map below for main locations, mentioned in the text. Oudemirdum is centered; locations OBW, OBL and OBL2 are just outside the map.

Map of a part of Gaasterland, taken from the AHN -map, with main location from the text

The find locations by community, location name, coordinates and number of artifacts found at the locations are shown in the table below.

Location code	Location name	Community *	Coordinates**	N
OLW1/2	Liemerige Wei	Oudemirdum	N 52.839, E 5.542	52
ORS1/ 2	Rinia State 2	Oudemirdum	N 52.850, E 5.546	58
OHP	Hunnings Paed	Oudemirdum	N 52.846, E 5.522	2
OHB	Hege Bouwen	Oudemirdum	N 52.852, E 5.545	3
OJB	Jolderen Bos	Oudemirdum	N 52.849, E 5.524	5
OBL2	Beukenlaan 2	Oudemirdum	N 52.868, E 5.540	2
OFW	Fontein Wei	Oudemirdum	N 52.856, E 5.526	1
OBL	Beukenlaan	Oudemirdum	N 52.863, E 5.533	1
OBW	Oude Balksterweg	Oudemirdum	N 52.864, E 5.531	1
OHB2	Hege Bouwen	Nijemirdum	N 52.853, E 5.554	3
			<i>Total artifacts</i>	128

*Names of parts of the newly formed community “De Friese Meren”(2014)

** Coordinates by Google Maps, appointing the field location (without address)

At these sites, ORS Oudemirdum *Rinia State*, located east of Oudemirdum, and at OLW1/2 Oudemirdum *Liemerige Wei 1/2*, located south of Oudemirdum most artifacts were noticed (respectively 52 and 58). These numbers of artifacts are not especially high in comparison with sites discovered elsewhere, but regarding the geological conditions, the time spend on field walking at these locations, more is to be expected here in case of follow up field -walking.

The difference in numbers of artifacts by all locations, enumerated in the table above, is

highly depending on the local circumstances at the different locations. For example, location OFW is a path in the forest- partially covered with dead leaves; OJB is woodland, where some artifacts were found at sandy footpaths, whereas OLW1 is an open, gently sloping well plowed arable field, where the top soil horizon has been removed in the 17th or 18th century, for which reason artifacts from deeper horizons have been exposed. While the difference in total numbers of artifacts collected at different locations is highly depending on the landscape, another factor is the time period of accessibility of the locations; e.g. the prospection of OLW1 took place in only 3 days, because that was all the time available, while at ORS over 12 days have been used for the prospectations. Other important factors influencing the outcome are the experience of the prospector, the depth of plowing, the coincidence if artifacts appearing at the surface, previous prospectations by others (carried out artifacts) and changing weather conditions, influencing visibility of artifacts at the surface (see e.g. Johnson, 1977; Cherry, Davis & Mantzourani, 1991). So the total numbers of artifacts and tool types do not reflect real activity levels and only give an average view. The artifacts are discussed in section 5.

Most of the locations are part of a higher moraine landscape, except for OBL2 (former source area of the brook valley of the Luts) and OHB, which is part of a sand blown valley at the lower part of ORS.

4.1 OLW1 Oudemirdum *Liemerige Wei*

The findspot OLW1 is located at the Liemerige Wei, south of Oudemirdum, with fieldname “The Hege Gerzen”, one of the higher parts of the end moraine (+ 4.16 N.A.P. [AHN2]).

The field is sloping to the north, and the coversand has been partially removed for the construction of a wall as a parcel boundary for holding sheep in the 17-18th century, which is very well visible by the outcropping red boulder-clay, in which direct context also many grey shards occur, possibly as waste material of 12- 14th century pottery activities (turntable pottery and handmade pottery). The red boulder-clay sometimes is mixed with the boulder- sand, which dries out rather quickly. Shards of Iron age pottery, (Streepband- pottery) found together with the handmade pottery from the 12th – 14th century (e.g the well to date “*Besenstrich* pottery”) makes it possible soil from elsewhere has been imported as a fertilizer, but I did not find good evidence for it.

The find-spot is indicated at the map below (at the blue triangle).

The location of OLW is located at ca 300 m from the current lake IJsselmeer; in the map, the large depression to the north is visible, remains of a glacial depression, which was most likely filled with open water or contained a brook system during the prehistoric.

Prehistoric flint artifacts were noticed in a relatively limited area of approx. 80 by 50 meters, located at two plowed fields [OLW1/OLW2] and intersected by a wall, forming a north east oriented elevation in the landscape. The intersection by the wall only has a meaning in appointing an exact location, flint artifacts appear at both sides, especially in the historic removed section along the wall and adjacent colluvial topsoil.

In the published article in December 2013, (see note 1 in this article) a total number of 62 flint artifacts were mentioned for analysis. In a new analysis, three of these artifacts are finally determined as debitage waste (in size ca 10 mm by 10 mm and 1 mm thick), which would give no further information, so these were deleted from the list. From the remaining 59 artifacts another 7 were still disapproved, because the features for man-made artifacts were not fully present or far too diffuse. So a total of 52 artifacts were validated and analyzed (see table 1 in this paragraph).

During analysis it was clear not all artifacts possess main features like a bulb and scar. Partially this is caused by the technological type of the artifact, as e.g. cores or tools on cores do not show such signs (except negative flake removal scars) partially because we deal with (distal) parts of artifacts, or the lack of such signs disappeared by secondary retouch of the proximal part of an artifact. A total of 26 artifacts (= 50 %) possesses a bulb -scar complex.

Table 3 Artifacts from OLW1. Sizes in mm and maximum values; BS= Bulb-Bulbar Scar present; Col.: color-type in grey with varieties (G) or honey/translucent (H); TB = Truncated Blade or part of it

Id	Tech	Length	Width	Thick	Col.	Typology	Remarks	BS
001	Flake	30	18	6	H	Scraper	Steep retouch / patina's	BS

002	Flake	35	21	8	G	-	Notched/ oblique Retouched TB	-
003	Flake	31	16	5	H	Drill	Burin drill	-
004	Flake	30	30	5	G	-	Decortication flake	BS
005	frost	41	17	6	-	-	REJECTED	
006	Flake	25	20	5	H	Scraper	Step fraction	BS
007	Flake	30	20	6	G	-	transverse scar	BS
008	Flake	31	13	3	H	Endscraper	Retouch	BS
009	Flake	28	20	5	G	Endscraper	Retouch	BS
010	Flake	21	21	5	G	-	Correctional flake;double scar	BS
011	Flake CF	-	-	-	-	-	REJECTED	
012	Flake	25	20	6	H	Scraper	chunk; transverse scar	BS
013	Flake	31	21	4	G	-	Debris	BS
014	Flake	21	11	5	G	Drill	Burin drill	BS
015	Flake	32	15	5	H	Scraper	Notched	BS
016	Flake	22	19	5	G	Drill	Distal part	-
017	Flake	21	20	5	G	Drill	Burin drill	BS
018	Flake	21	18	4	H	-	Cf. B, No S	B
019	Core	19	28	11	G	Scraper	Heavy tool on core	-
020	Core	42	30	10	G	Scraper	Or setup point; convergent scraper	-
021	Flake	-	-	-	-	Natural	REJECTED	
022	Core	32	22	6	H	Point	Semi finished. Surface retouch	-
023	Flake	18	18	2	H	-	Correction flake	BS
024	Core	41	31	12	G	Borer	Heavy tool on core; ret. Point Cortex	-
025	Flake	-	-	-	-	-frost-	REJECTED	-
026	Flake	25	17	6	G	-	Correction flake	BS
027	Core	32	22	17	G	endscraper	Retouch at one side; 3 platforms (flake removals)	
028	Blade	47	17	4	G	Scraper	Retouched blade With cortex	BS
029	Flake	22	22	5	G	-	Core preparation	

ID	Tech	Length	Width	Thick	Col.	Typology	Remarks	BS
030	Core	40	20	13	H		Flake core	-

031	Core	42	31	10	H	Scraper	Flake core / setup	-
032	Core	24	23	8	G	-	Core, 2 platforms	
033	Flake	30	21	8	G	Drill	Burin drill, large bulb scar	BS
034	Flake	30	18	5	G	-	No scar visible	B
035	Core	32	20	7	white	Flaked core	Burned flint	
036	Core	27	20	8	H	Scraper	One retouched side / flake core	-
037	Flake	20	19	5	H	-		BS
038	Flake	23	18	5	H	-	Ribbles/ retouch	-
039	Flake	21	20	4	G	Scraper		BS
040	Core	39	30	9	G	Point?	Adapted core	-
041	Core	22	18	16	G	Borer	Retouched	BS
042	Core	25	18	8	G	-	Broken flake core	-
043	Flake	27	16	4	G	-	No 2 nd retouch	BS
044	Core	31	22	8	G	Scraper	2 flake removals / scraper on core	-
045	Flake	-	-	-	-	-	REJECTED	
046	Core cf.	21	15	15	white	chunk	Burned flint	
047	Flake	20	10	2	H	Knife	Lame a dos naturel; notch	BS
048	Flake	14	10	3	H	-	-	BS
049	Flake	22	18	4	G	-	Part of decortication flake	-
050	Flake	28	22	3	H	-	Correction flake	BS
051	Flake	15	13	4	G	-	Ripples, patinas	BS
052	Flake	12	10	4	G	Scraper	Micro scraper, meso?	BS
053	Flake	20	18	5	H	Hollow scraper	Notched	BS
054	Blade	22	8	4	H	-	Montbani type Ventral flake negative	-
055	Core	31	18	10	G	Burin	Burin on core	-
056	Core	22	22	12	White		Burned flint	
057	Core	50	37	20	G	Drill	Heavy drill on core	-
058	Chunk	-	-	-	-	-	REJECTED	
059	Core	25	19	8	G	Point?	Adapted core, notch	-
060	-	-	-	-	-	-	REJECTED	

061	Blade	28	10	5	G	-	Fragment of a blade/ TB	-
062	flake	10	10	1	H	-	Debris flakelet	BS

Out of 52 (N= 52) a total of 34 (65%) are flakes. Most flakes are of the tertiary type, but secondary flakes occur (3 = 8%, N= 34). Dorsal bulbar scars are mostly high positioned on the flake, supposing production by a soft hammer technique (see e.g. Stafford, 2001) Sometimes, bulbar scars are in lower position and transverse. A total of 19 irregular cores are counted, (36%, N= 52), while blades at this site are very rare (2 blades from a total of 52 = 4%). Tool production was easy to establish by the many cores (19), decortication flakes and core-preparation flakes (8) and some debris (2). The small numbers of debris (2) in the total number of artifacts might be explained by the bad visibility of such small parts and moreover, these are difficult to distinguish from natural flint. In the cf.- group several objects ended by the lack of a clear bulb- scar, while at the same time percussion ripples or other flaking evidence was present. The flake core OLW-030 is an example of raw material use, as only three ventral flake negatives are visible at the core, so the core has been rejected without really using it completely. Obviously there has been a big choice in raw materials, so they only could take the most convenient flint type. Another indication for tool production at the site is given by the limited numbers of the bulb – scar complex at the artifacts which is only 27/ 52 = 51 %. This large number with a lack of an important, in prospection methods pre- selected primary determination feature is of course formed by cores, broken proximal parts of flakes, core preparation flakes, but also by semi finished tools, like points and convergent scrapers on cores, or, in case of retouched proximal ends.

In this analysis, it is clear flakes and cores at findspot OLW were the dominant artifact types while blades do not occur frequently. This would reflect two different aspects of the tool production strategy. At first, this would reflect the limits of possible tool processing from the type of raw flint available, which would have been surface collected and though of good, sufficient quality, of limited dimensions, at least for the usable part. Building platforms for blade reduction is not easy on irregular cores, so a part of it gets lost. Another aspect could be given by the fact no blades would have been necessary for the tasks to carry out (scraping, cutting, boring), or would not fit in the tradition (especially during the transition from Middle Neolithic to Late-Neolithic- Bronze Age). The single inverse retouched blade found at OLW1 was half covered with cortex and could be regarded as a used decortication flake.

In size we distinguish a certain homogeneity, flakes and cores mostly ranging in length between 20 and 40 mm, with single exceptions of 10 mm and 50 mm in length and an average of 27.5 mm (appendices, chart 1). The width of the artifacts mostly has dimensions between 15 and 23 mm with average of 19, 3 mm (appendices, chart 2). The thickness varies between 1 and 20 mm, average is 6, 7 mm.

Like at other tool- production locations with abundant raw materials (e.g. at Banholt, South- Limburg), cores were rejected before they were completely used up; meanwhile, a secondary use of cores as ‘heavy duty’ tools (borer, scraper) was normal (12 reused cores out of 19).

In tool typology, only 52 % (N= 27) of the artifacts could be determined for its type and possible related function. This small number is due to the obvious tool production

purposes of the site: this unless the secondary use of tools; likewise decortication flakes and preparation flakes were rejected immediately, so these are not artifacts of any typology and only reflect use in a technological stage.

Another factor would be, well shaped tools have been exported to other places, to use them elsewhere. The rejection of the semi – finished point, with an invasive non-parallel retouch, is obviously the result of a mistake, explaining the discard of some artifacts.

At third, we must not forget the prospecting only show a random picture of what is visible on the surface and many artifacts would still be in the terrain.

In this article, the division in two main color-types is made for practical purposes.

Slight variations are visible for both types, like grey- brown, grey- black, orange- honey, yellow -honey, etc.; in main groups these are divided into grey (G) and honey (H) as these are the dominant color types. The number of grey color- type flint is 30, honey color- type 19 and white (burned) flint 3. We might conclude the grey color type was in favor over the more translucent honey colored flint type, though the last one is a beautiful translucent flint of good quality. In the remaining deviant flint colors, a good quality brownish - black colored flint has been noticed.

Raw material use by main color of the flint at OLW; Grey = 30, Honey = 19 and burned (white) 3. (N=58)

Technological types of OLW; Flakes = 34, cores = 19 and blades = 2. (N= 52)

Artifacts are relatively thick. When we leave the thickness of cores out of the statistic overview, the average thickness of the tools (defined in typology) on flakes is 4,5 mm (N= 14, of which 8 are 5 mm thick) while the tools on cores have an average thickness of

11,6 mm. Flakes are with expressive bulbs but relative small platforms. It is likely a soft hammer technique has been used for the production of the smaller flakes. This is also proven by the gently concave shape of the flakes.

4.2 ORS1 /ORS2 Oudemirdum *Rinia State*

This location is a large (double) arable field north of the mansion *Rinia State* at Oudemirdum. The field is in altitude ranging between ca. + 5, 5 m N.A.P. and ca. + 2, 9 m N.A.P. and adjacent to a large (sand blown) depression, where deep ditches form a large drain system of the area. It is a gently to the north sloping field, with visible water-source activity in the higher parts after heavy rainfall, causing water running for days after a period of rain.

This field shows clear erosional effects, where the boulder clay horizon has been mixed with coversand; many stones, including (natural) flint exposed at the surface and a part of the field was difficult to access after rainfall. The context in this case has been very disturbed: both by sloping colluvial layers and plowing activities.

The coordinates of the find location of the transverse point at field ORS2 is N 52.848976, E 5.545931 (appointed by Google Maps). A total of 58 artifacts were noticed at this divided field (with codes ORS1 and ORS2), where natural flint is very common at the surface (as a proof of deep plowing, as a result of the construction of drain pipes in the field and because of erosion). Artifacts were found both at ORS1 and ORS 2, for ORS1 the coordinates of the find location are N 52.850816, E 5.546274, given by Google Maps. Artifacts, found at an altitude of only ca +3 m. N. A. P. probably have sloped down, as heavy erosion occurred in 2013. Artifacts in blade technology only were found at the highest part of the field (ORS1). A large core (chunk, ORS-046) with flaking scars (small negatives) in similar patina's is showing the raw material choice of the flint knappers. One part of the large core has been adapted to form a heavy drill. This grey type flint is forming the majority of the raw material used for the tools.

Raw material choice by color type at ORS1/ORS2. Grey =37, Honey= 16 and white- grey dotted (non- local) 3 (N=58)

Technological types of ORS1/ORS2. Cores =17, Blades =9,Flakes = 30 and chunks =2. (N=58)

Image above: the assumed, simplified paleogeographic situation at fields with code ORS1 and ORS 2 projected on the current AHN map; assumed Mesolithic- Neolithic site in the red elongated circle. Oudemirdum and the area north of Rinia State were forming a large source region, which fed a brook, that flew into a northeastern direction- towards the present Sminkewei. More sites are to be expected in this region.

Table 4 Artifacts from ORS1 and ORS2; Sizes in mm and maximum values; BS= Bulb-Scar present; Col.: color-type in grey with varieties (G) or in honey/translucent (H); TB = Truncated Blade or part of it

Id	Tech	Length	Width	Thick	Col.	Typology	Remarks	BS
001	Core	25	20	10	G	Scraper	Notched	
002	Flake	35	22	6	G	Burin	-	BS
003	Flake	33	23	5	G	Backed knife	Backed knife Retouched back	BS
004	Flake	19	18	5	H	Scraper	notched	BS

005	Flake	31	20	4	H	-	Setup point	BS
006	Blade	13	10	2	H	Transverse point		-
007	Flake	15	12	2	H	Waste	Ripples of percussion	-
008	Flake	13	13	3	H	Waste	TB proximal end of blade	-
009	Flake	21	20	4	H	Scraper	Notched/ retouch	-
010	Flake	18	20	2	H	-	-	BS
011	Chunk	11	8	2	H	Waste	Debris: micro-triangle?	BS
012	Flake	12	14	2	G	Microburin	-	BS
013	Flake	12	8	1	G	-	flakelet	BS
014	Flake	15	13	2	G	-	Part of flake/ ret.	S
015	Flake	31	17	2	H	Knife	Lame à dos naturel	BS
016	Blade	10	10	2	H	Transverse point	No BS	-
017	Flake	20	13	2	H	-	Decortication flake	BS
018	Blade	20	9	2	G	-	Bladelet	BS
019	Core	22	18	6	G	-	Mesolithic blade core; 5 blade negatives	
020	Flake	26	18	4	H	Scraper	Use retouch	BS
021	Flake	20	13	4	H	Scraper cf.		
022	Core	40	30	18	G	Scraper	Retouched core with cortex	
023	Blade	40	15	10	G	Knife	Backed, retouched	
024	Core	43	21	20	G		Blade negatives visible	
025	Core	30	12	3	G	Scraper	Retouched blade core	
026	Flake	20	18	3	H	Drill	Notched, heavy ripples;bipolar?	BS
027	Blade	22	10	2	H	Knife	TB obliquely broken	-
028	Flake	28	22	5	G	Borer	Notched	BS
029	Flake	28	13	5	G	Scraper	Cortex/ retouch	BS
030	Flake	31	18	12	G	Knife	Backed knife / patina's	-
031	Core	32	13	5	Whi	-	Blade core	-

					te			
032	Blade	22	12	3	G	Borer	Retouched blade Imported flint	BS
033	Core	22	22	9	G	-	With blade neg.	
034	Blade	25	20	5	G	Scraper	Wide blade	BS
035	Blade	40	11	8	H	Drill	Part of blade*	-
036	Blade	27	8	3	H		Retouched notch	-
037	Flake	31	28	11	G	Scraper	'Flaked flake'	BS
038	Flake	18	9	3	G	Knife/Scraper	Inverse retouch 60 % cortex	BS
039	Flake	21	18	5	G	Scraper		BS
040	Core	38	21	6	G	Scraper	Scraper on core/ flake neg.	-
041	Core	35	33	11	G	-	Flake core + ret.	
042	Core	25	20	13	G	-	Flake core 3 platforms	
043	Flake	18	20	5	G	-	Prox.part of TB	BS
044	Flake	12	14	3	H	-	Unret. flake	BS
045	Core	41	28	4	White	-	Ret. Montbani type blade	-
046	Chunk	70	50	50	G	Raw material	Flake neg./ + ret.	-
047	Flake	15	12	3	White	scraper	Micro scraper distal part; steep ret.	-
048	Flake	28	25	10	G	-	Distal part. B cf.	-
049	Core	42	28	10	G	-	Split pebble core, type 'slice'	-
050	Flake	22	23	6	G	-	Notch , steep retoch	BS
051	Flake	40	32	10	G		Debitage	
052	Core	52	50	13	G	Borer	Notch, ret. heavy tool	
053	Core	43	44	13	G	scraper	Bifacial ret.	
054	Core	43	12	3	G		Blade core; inverse retouch + notch at prox. end	BS
055	Flake	43	22	7	G	End-scraper	Step fracture;	-
056	Core	30	15	5	G	-	Split pebble; flake neg.	-
057	Flake	26	16	5	G		Unret. flake	BS

- Parts of blades are counted as well, even though this might cause a biased view in total flint artifacts, see e.g. Hiscock about consequences

4.3 OHP Oudemirdum *Hunnings Paed*

This is a plowed field (altitude + 10, 9 m N.A.P.) [AHN2] located at the south side of the end moraine not far from the highest point of the region. As a part of the wider sand ridge, the two artifacts are rather disappointing, more artifacts were expected here. The prospection only took place at one morning in a limited part of the area as a part of the field had been plowed. Some information about this particular location adjacent to the south of the village of Oudemirdum was given by a local inhabitant (Mr. Twijnstra) about a filled –up, ring- shaped structure, which had been visible after plowing the field located north and east of OHP; is this feature the remains of a structure and how to interpret this? Maybe as a Bronze Age barrow, comparable with such structure found in Brugge (Belgium, see Hillewaert & Hoorne, 2006); it is very possible late Neolithic to early Bronze Age activity can be found especially at these locations; in this case the sections between ca + 9 m. N. A.P. and + 4 m. N. A. P., located to the south are suitable location for prospectations, depending on the erosion at this field.

Table 5 Artifacts from OHP; Sizes in mm and maximum values; BS= Bulb- Scar present; Col.: color-type in grey with varieties (G) or in honey/translucent (H); TB = Truncated Blade or part of it

Id	Tech	Length	Width	Thick	Col.	Typology	Remarks	BS
001	Core	22	20	5	H		Flake core	BS
002	Flake	31	18	5	H		Flake	BS

4.4. OHB Oudemirdum *Hege Bouwen*

This field is a plowed field at + 2.7 m N.A.P. [AHN2] that could be considered as an extension of ORS1/2.

Coversand is dominating the field, and natural flint is rare. Two artifacts were found at this location. Two other flint objects are uncertain (cf.) and not counted.

Table 6 Artifacts from OHB; Sizes in mm and maximum values; BS= Bulb- Scar present; Col.: color-type in grey with varieties (G) or in honey/translucent (H); TB = Truncated Blade or part of it

Id	Tech	Length	Width	Thick	Col.	Typology	Remarks	BS
001	Core	22	20	7	G	-	Flake negatives	BS
002	Core	31	18	8	G	-	2 blade neg. visible	-

4.5 OJB Oudemirdum *Jolderen Bos*

The Jolderenbos is a small forest or woodland located at the end moraine just southwest of Oudemirdum. The forest has been drained by ditches, to allow trees to root. Some sand paths are leading through the wood.

A total of five artifacts have been in the woodland of Jolderenbosch; it's clear these originate from eroding surfaces. In technology the artifacts consist of one blade and four

flakes, among it one flakelet, obvious made in a micro- debitage technique. One flake has been processed to serve as a point in weaponry. It's just by accident this arrow point has been discovered at + 17, 93 m N.A.P. [AHN2] and exact coordinates N 52.849987, E 5.524173 (adjusted by Google Maps); later, in the vicinity some other artifacts have been found. The point is a typical guide artifact for the Late Neolithic, and its reduced shape is rather Late Neolithic than Early Bronze Age, the latter are more elongated in shape and do not possess a shaft thorn. The point is similar to one of the six points, found in the forge's grave at Lunteren (*Veluwe* region The Netherlands) attributed to the Late Beaker Culture (Kooijmans et al. (ed.), 2005). This would justify placing the point in the period between ca. 2200 and ca 2000 BC. Though the raw material of the found artifacts is mainly a honey colored flint type, there is no cohesion in tool technology and it is impossible to tell if they belong to a same period.

Table 7 Artifacts from OJB; Sizes in mm and maximum values; BS= Bulb- Scar present; Col.: color-type in grey with varieties (G) or in honey/translucent (H); TB = Truncated Blade or part of it

Id	Tech	Length	Width	Thick	Col.	Typology	Remarks	BS
001	Blade	32	14	6	H	Ret. blade		BS
002	Flake	30	22	9	H	-		BS
003	Flake	22	16	3	H	Point	Surface retouch, concave base	-
004	Flake	13	8	2	H	-	Flakelet (micro)	BS
005	Flake	21	19	8	G	Scraper	+ cortex >60 %	BS

4.6 OBL2 Oudemirdum *Beukenlaan 2*

This is a plowed field north of Oudemirdum. The difference between elevation lines is suggesting a small depression in the south- eastern part of the field, possibly a former pond. The altitude of the field is ca + 1.05 N.A.P., while the depression is ca 0, 5 m N.A.P. (AHN2]. This area could be regarded as a pond area - together with the area opposite of the Sminkewei, located nearby the source area of the former Luts brook, an attractive area for prehistoric people.

Artifacts were found at the elevation; at an altitude of ca. 1 m. N. A. P. The roundabout retouched scraper has no further characteristics and could be placed in the broad Neolithic- Bronze Age period.

Table 8 Artifacts from OBL2; Sizes in mm and maximum values; BS= Bulb- Scar present; Col.: color-type in grey with varieties (G) or in honey/translucent (H); TB = Truncated Blade or part of it

Id	Tech	Length	Width	Thick	Col.	Typology	Remarks	BS
001	Core	27	23	7	G	Scraper	Roundabout ret.	BS
002	Flake	21	16	4	H	Scraper	Notch	BS

4.7 OFW Oudemirdum *Fontein Wei*

This location at + 10, 5 m N.A. P. (AHN2] is a footpath in the forest, in fact the access

road to a war monument of Oudemirdum. Due to erosion, between natural flint, 1 certain and 3 uncertain artifacts has been noticed. The location is a south oriented sloping path, directly at a geological steep edge, the boundary between the former moorland and the sandy upland.

Table 9 Artifacts from OFW; Sizes in mm and maximum values; BS= Bulb- Scar present; Col.: color-type in grey with varieties (G) or in honey/translucent (H); TB = Truncated Blade or part of it

Id	Tech	Length	Width	Thick	Col.	Typology	Remarks	BS
001	Core	20	15	5	G	-	S= transverse	BS

4.8 OBL Oudemirdum Beukenlaan

This field is located at the Beukenlaan in Oudemirdum, at an east oriented part of the local part of the end moraine, slightly sloping to the west, where the ridge is visible. The altitude of the field is ca + 1, 8 m N.A.P. [AHN2], where the top of the ridge has an average altitude of ca. + 3, 4 m. N. A. P. [AHN2]. A small pond, locally named *dobbe*, has been muted in 2013, the year of the prospection. This pond, perfect round in form had a depth of ca 1, 3 m. As the field has been ‘polluted’ with imported peat soil, original horizons were not always well visible. During first prospectations, this peat soil was not present and the cover sands still were accessible for prospectations. Besides of a single prehistoric artifact, many shards were found here. Artifacts from the prehistory might be expected in the pasture land right east of the field and located higher on the ridge.

Table 10 Artifacts from OBL; Sizes in mm and maximum values; BS= Bulb- Scar present; Col.: color-type in grey with varieties (G) or in honey/translucent (H); TB = Truncated Blade or part of it

Id	Tech	Length	Width	Thick	Col.	Typology	Remarks	BS
001	Core	31	30	13	G	Scraper	Core scraper/patina	-

4.9 OBW Oudemirdum Oude Balksterweg

This field, adjacent to OBL, is of the same land -owner. Here we are at the ridge, at an altitude of ca. + 3, 5 m. N.A.P. [AHN2].

Table 11 Artifacts from OBW; Sizes in mm and maximum values; BS= Bulb- Scar present; Col.: color-type in grey with varieties (G) or in honey/translucent (H); TB = Truncated Blade or part of it

Id	Tech	Length	Width	Thick	Col.	Typology	Remarks	BS
001	Core	56	51	40	G	Borer cf.	Flake negatives /heavy point	-

4.10 OHB2 Nijemirdum Hege Bouwen

Field in the bend of the road between Oudemirdum and Nijemirdum at an altitude of ca. 4,

2 m. N. A. P. [AHN2], where some flint artifacts were noticed among shards from the 11th and 12th century. One of the artifacts has the appearance of a small harvesting knife (see image at appendices).

Table 12 Artifacts from OHB2; Sizes in mm and maximum values; BS= Bulb- Scar present; Col.: color-type in grey with varieties (G) or in honey/translucent (H); TB = Truncated Blade or part of it

Id	Tech	Length	Width	Thick	Col.	Typology	Remarks	BS
001	Core	34	30	16	G		Brown color / flake neg. +ret.	-
002	Flake	32	13	5	G	Knife	Broken / part of flake	-
003	Flake	20	18	6	H		Retouched flake	BS

4.11 All artifacts from the 2013 field inspections.

Artifacts are in general irregular and not fine finished tools.

Flaking is the most abundant tool production technology applied on the found artifacts from all prospected sites. This is not only visible in the large numbers of regular flakes compared to blades, but also by the large numbers of cores with flake negatives (see also diagram below).

Division in blades, flakes and cores over all artifacts Flakes = 72; Cores = 44; blades = 12 (N= 128)

The most used flint type to produce flint tools from local flint is grey (75) and honey (43) (N= 118). This mainly does reflect the purpose of the tool, as the grey flint type looks slightly more granular, (less translucent) so this would be better for tasks where more force is given on the artifact (see also tool function and color in next paragraph).

5. Prehistoric tools from Gaasterland

From all artifacts, tools are especially interesting, as they might reveal a possible function for the prehistoric people. Especially in conclusions about possible settlement and type-site (base- camp, seasonal camp, short hunting camp, shortstop, etc.) tools are crucial, as they reflect the type of tasks people have carried out at the site.

In this article, in absence of wear analysis, only basic functional features of tools are described, to estimate possible activities the tools were made for. Tool types from the

different locations are presented in the table below:

Location	Knife	Scraper	Burin	End-scraper	Drill	Borer	Point
OLW	1	12	1	3	6	2	3
ORS	6	14	2	1	2	3	1
OJB	-	1	-	-	-	-	1
OHP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
OBW	-	-	-	-	-	1	-
OBL2	-	2	-	-	-	-	-
OHB	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
OFW	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
OBL	-	1	-	-	-	-	-
OHB2	1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Sub-total	8	30	3	4	8	6	5
Total tools	64						

Table, showing the tool types from various locations

In possible tool function, 64 (50 %,) of total finds (N= 128) could be determined and categorized as ‘tool’ in typology with its probable function. So, half of all found artifacts, not assigned as a “tool”, must be regarded as artifacts involved in the debitage process, like flake- or blade- cores, decortication flakes and debitage waste.

A complicating factor in the interpretation of this overview is, we cannot treat all artifacts as if these form one assemblage from one period, as we probably deal at least with one palimpsest, namely at location ORS: the blade technique, where regular micro- blades were produced is very different from the flaking from multiplatform cores.

Generally, we cannot speak of a situation of high percentage debitage waste/ low percentage tools, as the ratio is 50/50. This justifies the assumption, tool production was carried out e.g. during other activities, - hunting- collecting- fishing, pointing at seasonal camps. Tools like scrapers were used for daily tasks like preparation of food and repairing clothing, but also for making and repairing the hunting equipment (bows, arrows, traps). Only five points are found, which is a contra- indication for the existence of real hunting camps; on the other hand, nice arrow heads would have been exported elsewhere. Honey colored flint type is more translucent and easier to break compared to the grey type color and its variations. In tool function, we distinguish following use of the color types, see pie diagram below.

Scrapers and color type. N= 30. Grey color type = 19, Honey color type = 11

Drills/ borers and color type. N= 14. Grey color type = 11. Honey color type =3

Tools are not sub divided in their tool form, such as side- scrapers, end- scrapers, etc.

Comparison between artifacts of ORS and OLW

The numbers of artifacts, found at the two find-locations are almost the same (52 and 58). At both sites, local flint has been used for tool production and the average dimensions show similar production of artifacts.

The average thickness at ORS is smaller, as micro- artifacts were included.

Scrapers, found at ORS, 10 artifacts were made of flint from the grey color type (N=14) and 4 from the honey color type (N= 14), while at OLW, these numbers are 6 flint artifacts were made from the grey color type (N=12) and in 6 from the honey color type (N=12). Micro -artifacts (with dimensions < 15 mm in length and < 12 mm in width) are in all cases made from the honey colored flint type,

6. The relation between artifacts and the landscape

As expected, prehistoric artifacts have been found at higher, eroded parts of the sand ridges of the glacial moraine. A clear relation with the landscape resides in the fact that people in prehistoric visited high and dry places, mostly in the vicinity of running water or wide open water. This is even the case with finds from OBL2, where the roundabout retouched scraper has been found at a small elevation in the former source area of the Luts -brook, an elevation only 0, 5 m higher than the surrounding area, which consisted of many small water containing depressions – ponds. At site ORS2 the artifacts were found at a place where after heavy rain running water flowed downward for days: the remains of a potential source area, located high upon the glacial moraine, where boulder clay-horizons influences the water-tables and three distinct sources could be noticed even today. No wonder, the land users were using drainpipes all over the field to drain the excess of water. Outcropping boulder clay horizons and mixed horizons (boulder- clay with boulder-sand, an altered glacial till residue) contain flint chunks, but also river rolled pebbles that have been transported by the ice cover during the Saalian complex. It is likely, running water caused outcropping horizons where flint was accessible by prehistoric people. At OLW1, a former source area is still visible, especially in summer time; in the late evening low gradient shadows in the landscape still show small height differences revealing an elongated depression that might be explained as a former brook

valley, which had its source in the higher part at the boulder clay, northwest of the field. The find spot is located at an elevated half- peninsula in a deep depression, which would have been surrounded by moorland. Parts of the Gaasterland region would have been easily accessible, while other parts were poorly drained and inaccessible, the higher parts of the end -moraine serving as a connecting corridor between marshland and brook lands. The depression east of Oudemirdum could be explained as a former brook system, where many small water-sources flowed together to form a wider brook land. Indeed, it looks like the southern ridge was a good place to stay, where small ponds on top of the end moraine (located to the north and northeast of the mansion *Rinia State*) provided attractive scenery for prehistoric people: running water in a well drained area, high enough to keep dry feet. At the top of this ridge, we find depressions, possible relics of former, prehistoric ponds.

This specific scenery like dry sand areas aside depressions with open water would have attracted prehistoric people, comparable with prehistoric activity zones in the Belgian Kempen (*Campine*) region (see Van Gils & De Bie, 2002).

Artifacts, found in Oudemirdum *Jolderenbosch* and Oudemirdum *Hunning Paed* , might justify the idea this highest point of the area has been used for prehistoric activities, not only because of its height, but also because it was located near a small brook flowing into southwestern direction and near large moorland areas to the north (west of Oudemirdum with a dried brook valley still visible west of the Beukenlaan) and to the southwest (direction of Mirns).

Predicting the locations of findspots for archaeological correlate or real sites by the study of the paleolandscape can be very useful (Banning 2002) but is equally highly depending on unpredicted post -depositional processes (both natural and human) and not always logical for disturbed contexts like plowed fields.

So, only an overall *indication* of potential suitable areas is justified, and the results of the prospectations in this article are therefore related to brief knowledge of a combination of N.A. P.- heights, interval lines and special soil conditions.

7. Conclusions

As all information in this article is required from surface collected artifacts, only very limited conclusions are possible. So these conclusions only give some general clues about artifacts and prehistoric activity in Gaasterland, based on one year field prospectations. All artifacts come from the broad late- Mesolithic - Early Bronze Age period, as no typical Paleolithic or Mesolithic artifacts were noticed (4). Some evidence about attribution of artifacts to a more focused period is given by guide artifacts, especially points.

The semi -finished point from OLW1 is typical for the Late Neolithic to Early Bronze Age and such points often have been found in the sandy regions of the Northern Netherlands. The artifacts found together with this semi- finished point are probably associated, especially regarding the limited area where artifacts have been found and the similar dimensions of the point compared to accompanying cores. The finds of the artifacts together with a relative large number of cores, of which some are definitely flaked cores, is suggesting a Late-Neolithic to Early Bronze Age activity zone (period: approximately between 2300 and 2000 BC) where tool production was an important part

of the activities; another part of the activities comprised small daily tasks, regarding the (used) scrapers and burin drills. Whether this task was e.g. repairing of the hunting equipment or if we might speak of real camp-sites where all kinds of tasks were carried out is not clear. Regarding the number of artifacts, found in a three days field walking campaign, the chance we have a real prehistoric camp site at this location is quite conceivable.

In the Jolderenbosch near Oudemirdum, a typical point with surface retouch and concave base has been found, which is related to the Beaker Culture and at ORS2 a transverse point, made on a truncated blade has been found and with regard to the elongated shape and the L-W indices in the transverse view, it is possibly from an early Neolithic period (see e.g. Niekus, 2008); stylistic features of the other accompanying artifacts would make a date in the Late Mesolithic period quite possible as well.

At site ORS1 artifacts with typical Mesolithic features were noticed (narrow blade and truncate blade technology), so a diffuse, transitional phase in the Late Mesolithic cannot be excluded either, especially for this region (5)

But all of these arrow- points, having been made from local flint, are bringing together a possible conclusion the activities in Gaasterland were not really short-term events. It is obvious we deal with special activities like tool production (6), but this probably would not have been the single reason to visit or dwell the region. After all, local flint had to be collected, prepared and processed, and the accompanying tools indicate operating tasks such as preparing food, repairing clothing and repairing and producing parts of the hunting equipment (borers, drills, scrapers), while the arrow- points are reflecting hunting activities.

More evidence about a possible longer stay in the region is derived from finds of burned flint from OLV1; usually interpret as coming from local hearths.

On the contrary, hardly any possible evidence (7) can be derived from these artifacts about a more sedentary life -style, but it is possible activities were temporary on a seasonal base, so the terrain might have served as a 'longer seasonal settlement'. In this case, the time spent on the field -prospections in this area has been far too short.

The field prospecting also were regarded as a test-case for field walking in a new environment, using some datasets for predicting prehistoric activity sites.(8)

From the 10 find locations, described in this article, 6 have been predicted as locations where prehistoric activity could be established by artifacts. Two locations, OBL and OBW were totally misinterpreted, even though at each field one artifact has been found, more prehistoric activity was expected. This low number of artifacts at these fields could also be due to geological circumstances or the way the field has been worked (imported soil).

Incidental, - sometimes single- finds of artifact, such as the artifacts from Oudemirdum *Fonteinwei*, Oudemirdum *Beukenlaan2* and Nijemirdum *Hege Bouwen* might reflect short -term activity sites (shortstops or breaks; incidentally used locations or random lost artifacts), but more prospecting would be necessary to make any conclusions; in this case, the absence of artifacts is on the other hand no evidence for absence of prehistoric activity.

An important research question for the region is the establishment of the TRB culture apart from the find of the stone coffin in the Rijsterbosch, Characteristic for the tendency in changing tool production strategies since the early Neolithic (i.c. the

Swifterbant - Culture) is the increasingly importance of flakes in the tool production (e.g. Devriendt, 2008), such as counts for the West-group of the TRB and the fact the TRB is predominantly limited in presence in dry sand-regions. As flaking is the case for the majority of the artifacts presented in this article - and moreover where blade technology is very rare, except for micro-debitage perhaps belonging to Late Mesolithic or Early Neolithic hunter gatherers - and because of the chronology of type artifacts suits with the occurrence of TRB in the Northern region of The Netherlands, it is possible parts of the found artifacts belong to the (later) TRB Culture. Another indication is made by the fact micro- burin technique is practically absent.

Finally, for a region like Gaasterland, evidence for any prehistoric activity is very welcome, especially because of the lack of a coherent view on the archaeological time -line of this region. Questions like “where did the people from the TRB that used the stone coffin live?” or “was the Gaasterland region inhabited – including real agricultural settlements- during the post- Mesolithic, or did Gaasterland have served for hunting- gathering- fishing purposes, similar to dry sand-regions in the Lower countries?” still are unanswered.

Off site archaeology can play an important role in the increase of the knowledge of archaeological chronology of the region, especially because the lack of artifacts from local stratigraphies and corresponding datable information until now.

As no information from excavations is available, field prospections, focused on the discovery of new sites in Gaasterland, can play a major role in the general knowledge of the prehistory, but at the same time spatial interpretation of datasets is always difficult as high density localities are noticed against a low density background, depending on special geological conditions (see e.g. Foley, 1981). This is especially the case in Gaasterland.

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Notes

(1) Groen, L.J. 2013; Een eenvoudige analyse van vuursteen artefacten van de Hege Gerzen bij Oudemirdum (Gemeente Friese Meren, Friesland) [internet publ. 5403705](#)

(2) No public reports about surface collected items from Gaasterland are known to the author. Reports of prehistoric finds from the region are stored in the official national ARCHIS system and could be found back in public at [archeologiet erfgoed theasaurus.nl](#) Prospections in a systematic surface survey (SSS) are carried out by the Fryske Akademy, but the outcome is unknown by the author. Short publications in the publication *Diggelgoud*, published by AFUK - see reference below this article

(3) See e.g. appendix 1 of ScARF, Lithic Identification and Analysis in ScARF download (Scottish Archaeological Research Framework) and the works of Odell and Andrefsky , see references below

(4) Not only in typology but more in weathering characteristics, such as patina's.

(5) The sandy Gaasterland region is a region with poor soil conditions and was not easy to cultivate during the Early –Middle Neolithic, only by a step- by step process this was the case; we even do not know whether the area of Gaasterland was really cultivated during the Neolithic, maybe the people from the TRB lived more to the south, where more fertile soil gave better opportunities for agriculture; so the area was very suitable for

hunting purposes, comparable with the Belgian Kempen area, where the Mesolithic continued during the Neolithization of the adjacent areas

(6) Stapert, 1985, about flint extraction sites; characteristic are a high percentage debitage waste and a low percentage finished tools. We find these locations in flint- rich regions where flint is outcropping

(7) Battered stones and other more large, possibly adapted/ used stone objects were noticed and one polishing stone has been found at OLW1, suggesting here we find a possible location where a longer stay of prehistoric people is not totally excluded.

(8) Datasets, based on current altitude, density and direction of elevation lines, geological features on maps (e.g. interpretation of former brook systems, valleys of parched brook systems and disappeared or virtually dried sources) and a large experience from the hills of South Limburg

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Yn Gaasterlân weblog, internet address <http://archeoga.blogspot.nl>

Appendices

1. Diagrams

Chart 1 (below) LW1 Spread of length of artifacts X= numbers Y = length; values in mm

Chart 2 (below) OLW1 Spread of width of artifacts X= numbers Y = width; values in mm

Chart 3 (below) OLW1 Spread of width of artifacts X= numbers Y = thickness; values in mm

Chart 4 (below) OLW1 Spread of numbers of artifacts with similar length

2. images of locations

Field sketch of OLW1 (October 2013), with indicated the stripped top horizon (rectangular parts indicated by BC – boulder-clay), dots are single finds of artifacts and arrows indicate sloping gradients. Drawing is not in scale

Findspots of some flint artifacts from OLW1, projected on the field; view by Google maps. LW1 = OLW1 and LW1A = OLW2. The real concentration was noticed at numbers 022, 008 and 052

3. Some images:

A selection of images of artifacts, presented in this article, are brought together to give examples of these artifacts. Some non -flint artifacts, found in the vicinity of the artifacts at the same locations, are presented here as well, without any further conclusions.

Late Neolithic - Early Bronze Age point made of local flint, found in the Jolderenbosch,

near Oudemirdum

Core with flake negatives and a retouched edge (core scraper) found in the lower part of location ORS1 near Oudemirdum. The artifact is a slice of a split pebble still covered with some cortex, with function of the handle part; flake removals show heavy percussion ripples, indicating hard hammer technique. The opposite edge, at the top of the artifact has been carefully retouched. It's function would have been a scraper.

Blade core with flake negative and notches; found at ORS1 near Oudemirdum. This artifact most probably is associated with the transverse point

Transverse point from location ORS2, made on a truncated blade core. These types of points were common until the TRB- period. Retouch at parallel sides is suggesting a post-Mesolithic date, while from the Middle Neolithic transverse points disappear.

Typical man- made flake with bulb and scar and a used edge. Found at HB2, Nijemirdum. The features look rather fresh, typical for (fine) sand -logged finds

Small R/A drill on a flake from OLW1. Retouched area of the edge is indicated in the image right by a dotted line

Heavy convergent scraper on a core, from field OLW1

Semi- finished point from OLW1, made of translucent honey- colored local flint.

ORS1 – 027 Oudemirdum TB
distal. Knife or scraper

ORS1 – 028 Oudemirdum
Flake with notch

OFW- 001 Dorsal view of a truncated blade from Oudemirdum Fonteinwei. Blade- core type, with a ventral transversal scar and a dorsal 'step fracture' caused by hard percussion technique.

OBW-001. single find from the location Oudemirdum Oude Balksterweg; an adapted flint chunk with some flaking negatives and an adapted, secondary retouched point, probably used as a heavy borer/ drill.

OBL2 -001 Scraper, "flaked core with retouch"

OWL1-028; Retouched blade (primary blade or decortication blade) with cortex, supposing all products were used.

OHB -002; parallel flaked flake. The original thick flake has been struck off by hard hammer percussion.

ORS1 – 053 Heavy bifacial scraper core

A total of 35 objects are rejected or categorized 'cf.' demonstrating it is not always easy to distinguish real artifacts from geofacts

OHB2-001 probably a small flint harvesting knife with gloss patina at the edge. The flake has been broken, given the slight concave bottom of the artifact

Images of non-flint artifacts

These images are added for completeness; all of these non- flint artifacts or other objects are found in the vicinity of the other flint artifacts.

ORS1 fossilized molar herbivore

ORS1 fossilized bone fragment

ORS2 polishing stone:
sharpening stone
(iron age or later)

OLW1 polishing stone with multi
concave surfaces

Concave surfaces might indicate polishing of stone axes. All sides of this stone have concave surfaces, forming possible 'negatives' of a stone axe head' form.
